

Assessment of lithium ion battery ageing by combined impedance spectroscopy, functional microscopy and finite element modelling

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HIGHLIGHTS

- Combination of EIS, microscopy and FEM to assess ageing in commercial LIBs.
- FEM analyses of the EIS spectra gives direct access to physical and chemical parameters.
- The approach allows for unambiguous extraction of ageing related parameters.
- Microscopy reveals conductive subsurface features related with electrode degradation.
- Non-invasive EIS measurements are confirmed independently by microscopy.

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ABSTRACT

Development of future battery generations and quality control of current lithium-ion battery (LIB) systems require reliable techniques for the characterization of the complex dynamic processes in batteries. Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) is an established tool for the electrochemical characterization of LIBs and the related ageing processes. Nevertheless, ensuring a reliable interpretation and validation of the impedance data remains challenging. Here we show how EIS complemented by microscopy data can be successfully used to follow battery ageing. We connect data from both methods in an electrochemical finite element model (FEM) to extract changes of intrinsic battery parameters, such as double layer capacitance, film resistance, exchange current density, and particle radii. Ageing mechanisms induced by cycling and temperature are investigated by EIS on commercial cells. Postmortem analysis of the anode and cathode electrodes is carried out to determine their initial micrometric and nanometric structure and to independently investigate morphological and electrical changes induced by ageing. While the obtained initial structural dimensions reduce drastically the number of adjustable parameters in the FEM model, which enables us to follow battery ageing processes noninvasively through the EIS spectra, the microscopy results of the aged cells prove independently the validity of the here presented approach.

1. Introduction

The generation and storage of green energy are two of today's major technical challenges, which will have a tremendous impact on how we will live in future. While lithium-ion batteries (LIB) are currently the

most effective rechargeable energy storage systems, a better understanding of their ageing mechanisms is needed to address the lifetime and safety concerns and make proper predictions for enhancing their performance [1].

As LIBs are composed of several interconnected components, there

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are various causes of battery ageing leading to capacity and power fading [2]. These processes are classified into chemical or mechanical degradation mechanisms [3]. The former includes electrochemical processes such as electrolyte decomposition, interface layer formation, binder decomposition, and loss of lithium [4]. Whereas, the latter is related to volume changes and the subsequent stress generated in the active material particles of the cell, such as cracks, loss of contact, and isolation to the current collectors [5].

There are several techniques used to characterize battery ageing which are bulk electric techniques, such as electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) [6], pulsed measurement methods, and direct current internal resistance (DCIR). These methods are applied on an intact battery (without disassembling) and, thus, enables characterization in realistic circumstances. Other characterization methods are *in-situ* methods, that require custom build electrochemical cells, such as optical, X-ray, and neutron imaging methods. Alternatively, *ex-situ* (*post-mortem*) methods are used which require disassembling the cell and investigating the different cell compartments. These methods comprise, for instance, atomic force microscopy, scanning electron microscopy and transmission electron microscopy (AFM, SEM, and TEM, respectively), and Raman microscopy. These investigations are beneficial when higher resolution and sensitivity are required [3].

The various microscopy techniques were used to investigate electrode degradation including interface films or cracks on electrode surfaces, or material degradation such as changes on particle surfaces or dissolution of transition metals [7–10]. For example, standard light microscopy was applied to detect electrode film growth, cracks in electrode coatings or deformation of electrodes. Scanning electron microscopy, which provides higher lateral resolution due to smaller de Broglie wavelengths of electrons compared to visible light [7,11], can detect changes on particle surfaces, particle cracks and exfoliation. AFM was applied to follow the solid electrolyte interface (SEI) formation on the anode electrode [12,13], as well as to understand the morphology, mechanical and electrical properties of electrodes [14–16]. Scanning electrochemical microscopy (SECM) has been successfully applied to characterize various LIB samples [17,18]. However, microscopy techniques on their own are rather invasive methods and often limited to the study of model systems, due to complex sample preparation procedures.

On the other hand, EIS is a powerful non-invasive method for the study of electrochemical and physical behaviours of all kinds of LIBs

[19–22]. A number of prognostic studies, which employ EIS to characterize battery performance at different operational conditions, have been reported. For example, EIS was applied for cell quality assessment [23], state of charge (SoC) and [24] state of health (SoH) estimation [25, 26], temperature monitoring [27,28], power fading characterization [29], and electrochemical ageing of batteries [30,31]. To follow the change of certain battery parameters with EIS, the acquired impedance spectra are plotted in the complex plane and are compared with simplified equivalent circuit models of the battery that are associated with electrochemical processes at various frequency ranges. In the complex impedance plot (Fig. 1a, lower panel), ageing effects can be seen in the spectra as a shift of the low-frequency part of the EIS curve (right side) to higher impedances, and an increase in the semicircle width and height as we show in Fig. 1a (lower panel). Overall, ageing is related to the change of only a few battery parameters, such as the charge transfer resistance and the film resistance at the electrode interphases [32].

However, it is worth noting that these characterization methods considered independently give only partial information on the various ageing mechanisms, thus a combination of these methods is needed. Additionally, electric circuit parameters, obtained from EIS, are practical from a technical and engineering point of view, since they are simpler to fit to the experimental data and require less computational efforts, though the physical interpretation of the model electrical parameters are ambiguous when assigning them to physical processes and are more prone to overfitting than physics-based models [34,35]. Also, it is hard to relate them with electrochemical and morphological degradation and ageing processes taking place at the battery electrodes [33].

Since the physics-based FEM models provide a direct link between the cell impedance and the physical model parameters, FEM models are a more powerful tool to provide physical and chemical information, allowing to get deeper insights into all aspects of the battery cell than equivalent circuit-based models. Despite these advantages, FEM models are more complex and some of the geometrical and chemical parameters are cross-correlated and influence the impedance spectra in similar ways. Thus, the experimentally obtained change in the impedance spectra cannot be unambiguously related to a specific degradation process. In order to make practical use of finite element models, the number of unknown parameters must be reduced. As shown in Fig. 1c, we, therefore, determine the geometrical parameters of the battery

Fig. 1. Definition of the electrochemical battery model by a multilevel electrical characterization approach. (a) The battery cycling process, capacity test measurements, and EIS impedance analyzer with four-wire connections (upper), the EIS analysis on a wide frequency range visualized in the complex plane (lower). (b) An electrochemical finite element model (FEM) is used to extract ageing relevant electrochemical parameters from the measured EIS data. (c) The nano-characterization techniques atomic force microscopy (AFM), all-electric AFM, and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) are used on cycled battery samples in order to define several battery physical parameters for the FEM modelling and to follow corresponding changes induced by battery cycling.

electrodes from the nanometer to the millimetre level using state-of-the-art microscopy techniques. Moreover, current sensing AFM and scanning microwave microscopy (SMM) allow us, also, to extract electrical information of the battery electrodes at the nanoscale level [36].

In this paper, we show how impedance spectroscopy of commercial 18650 LIBs, complemented by microscopy data, can be successfully used to follow battery ageing upon continuous cycling. We determine ageing relevant parameters via EIS data and electrochemical FEM, together with microscopic images of the aged cells. Finally, we introduce the FEM that allows us to draw out the ageing induced changes in order to correlate these results with those obtained by EIS and microscopy analysis.

2. Results

2.1. EIS spectroscopy

We studied the variation of impedance spectra of cylindrical 18650 LIB as a function of cycling number, SoC, cycling temperature, and display the resulting impedance spectra in Nyquist plots in Fig. 2 a, b, and c, respectively. The EIS spectra in Fig. 2a exhibit a systematic change from the pristine cell to 800 times cycled cell (at 100% SoC), which consists of a small shift in the EIS curve at the low frequency region (right side) and an increase in the depressed semi-circle radius and height. These changes can be mainly interpreted as a change of the cell solution resistance (R_{sol}), the interface resistance (R_{film}), the charge transfer resistance (R_{ct}), and the double layer capacitance (C_{dl}) (clearly noticed at higher cycle numbers). The increase in the ohmic resistances with the cycling number can be related to the growth of the interface layer on the anode and the degradation of the electroactive materials, which are the main reasons for LIB performance loss, and capacity drop (see Fig. S1 in the Supplementary Information). With ageing, the growth of the interface layer increases, being reflected in the impedance spectra by the appearance of a second depressed semi-circle radius (representing the film resistance, R_{film}) and change in height (representing the interface double layer capacitance) at lower frequencies. These changes get more pronounced at higher cycle numbers (see Fig. 2a). These observations agree with several EIS studies on battery-cycle ageing. Jiang et al., for example, studied how EIS spectra evolve with battery cycle ageing for a Li-ion cell measured at 50% SoC and showed that the ohmic resistance increases with a more pronounced change at higher cycles, as well as an increase in the semicircle height of the Nyquist plot [31]. Stroe et al. also noticed an increase in the ohmic resistance and charge transfer resistance, though only a small increase in the semicircle height

of the Nyquist plots was observed [37]. It is worth noting that the cycling process we applied to the cells in this study was based on a constant current profile on the full voltage range (see Section 5.1), nonetheless, this method could be also applied to cells aged with different cycling strategies, such as dynamic cycling, or different cycling voltage limits. Recent studies show how the type of C-rates used affect cells ageing, and they also investigate which battery parameters are typically more sensitive to the cycling C-rate than others [38,39].

Secondly, we studied the influence of the battery SoC on the measured impedance spectra of 18650 LIB cells cycled 600 times, as shown in Fig. 2b (other data sets for 0 to 900 times cycled cells are shown in Fig. S2 and Fig. S3 in the Supplementary Information). The impact of SoC on the cell impedance spectra is more evident at low SoC levels (e.g. 20%). The dominant process, while varying the SoC, is the charge transfer resistance (R_{ct}), identifiable by the radius of the depressed semicircle. In general, at high SoC and low SoC, the impedance is higher, in contrast to intermediate SoCs where the resistance goes through a minimum, and this effect is typically more prominent for aged cells [1,40]. During cell discharge, Li^+ ions are extracted from graphite and intercalated into the cathode, and at lower cell voltages this results in a higher cell impedance. The reduced performance at low SoCs is mainly caused by the low-rate extraction of Li^+ ions from the graphite anode at low stoichiometries and structural changes at the cathode related to the accommodation of these charges. The results are in good agreement with the results obtained from ageing studies presented in Refs. [41–43] for similar Li-ion cells based on the LiNiCoAlO_2 (NCA) chemistry. As in the study by Eddahech et al. [44], we observe that the intersection point of the impedance spectra with the x-axis in the complex plane changes, showing an increase in the size of the semi-circle with lower SoC values.

Thirdly, in Fig. 2c we cycled three fresh cells up to 100 cycles, each at a different ambient temperature (i.e. 10 °C, 24 °C and 45 °C) and the impedance spectra was measured at a 100% SoC (other SoC levels are shown in Fig. S4 in the Supplementary Information). From the EIS Nyquist plots, the temperature dependent ageing mechanisms are shown. The cell cycled at 24 °C shows the lowest overall impedance values (lower semi-circle radius and height) in contrast to the cells cycled at low and high temperatures, and the most pronounced change was measured for the cell cycled at a higher temperature (45 °C). At low temperatures, the predominant ageing mechanism is Li plating on the anode and the related reactions with the electrolyte [45] (see blue curve showing an increased semicircle radius and height). The intercalation of Li ions on the anode surface is shown to proceed abnormally at low temperatures, or high C-rate [46]. Whereas, at higher temperatures the

Fig. 2. The effect of the electrochemical cycling, state of charge (SoC), and cycling temperature (T) on the impedance spectra of LIB. All measurements were done on 18650 cells, with NCA cathode chemistry (2.5 Ah nominal capacity) using a galvanostatic excitation signal with 10 mHz–5 kHz frequency range. (a) Impedance spectra of a cell cycled at a different number of cycles (from 0 to 800), measured at 100% SoC and 24 °C. Changing circuit parameters are indicated with arrows on the spectra. (b) Impedance spectra measured for decreasing SoC at 600 cycles and 24 °C. (c) Impedance spectra of three identical cells independently cycled 100 times in a temperature chamber each at a specific temperature: 10 °C, 24 °C, and 45 °C. The EIS measurements of the three cells are done after a 24-h rest period at 24 °C and at 100% SoC.

composition of the SEI changes as the chemical species become more soluble, the electrolyte is decomposed and SEI film thickness increases. In addition, the cathode degradation is more pronounced leading to an increase of the internal resistance [47]. This is also shown in Fig. 2c (red curve) with the increase in the semicircle width (related to the charge transfer resistance R_{ct}) and height (related to the double layer capacitance C_{dl}) and the appearance of a second semicircle at low-intermediate frequencies.

Although we show how EIS changes under different operating and ageing conditions, it is still difficult to directly observe specific ageing phenomena and interfacial changes or to disentangle the anode and cathode contributions from the overall impedance response. Thus, FEM modelling supported by advanced microscopy methods is introduced to provide an accurate interpretation, especially for cycling ageing, as presented in the following sections.

2.2. Finite element modelling

In order to directly associate battery cell ageing with the corresponding change of relevant electrochemical parameters, we implemented a FEM of the LIB that allows us to calculate impedance spectra as a function of the electrochemical and geometrical model parameters, such as the exchange current density, the electrode particle radii, etc. In the last section, we will use this model and solve the inverse problem by fitting the model to experimental EIS data and extract physical parameters from it. A sketch of the 1D FEM consisting of the micrometric anode and cathode with the separator in between is shown in Fig. 3a. The dimensions and the main modelled electrochemical processes are noted in the sketch and further details are found in the 'Materials and Methods' section. While this FEM, following the well-known Newman model [48], is only one-dimensional [49], it captures the mesoscale processes, as shown in Fig. 1b, through several coupled differential equations. The differential equations describe the non-isothermal charge/discharge process including the lithium material balance in the electrolyte. Overall, during a charging process of a battery, solvated Li^+ ions transfer across the interface layers and undergo intercalation in the anode. In this process, the solution resistance (R_{sol}) is related to liquid phase ion diffusion, which occurs across the separator towards the

electrode surface. The interface resistance and capacitance, R_{film} and C_{if} , respectively, are associated with the hindered liquid phase ion diffusion that occurs through the interface layer. The charge-transfer resistance (R_{ct}) is related to the mechanism allowing intercalation/de-intercalation of the Li^+ ions, and the double layer capacitance (C_{dl}), is related to the ionic interphase layer formed between the external surface of the active material particle and the electrolyte phase. These main parameters change with regards to the thickness and porosity of the electrodes, the active material particle radius, and the SoC of the electrodes, which are all parameters that are used in the FEM.

In Fig. 3b–d, we show the calculated impedance spectra simulation results while varying several model parameters, especially those related to battery ageing. However, other parameters could also be investigated with the proposed model, for example, the change in thickness of the electrodes. In Fig. 3b, increasing the electrode film resistance results in an increase in the width and height of the semicircle in the Nyquist plot. In comparison to the measured EIS on cycled batteries, as shown in the previous section, this was a common effect noticed for our different ageing mechanisms, such as the electrochemical cycling ageing, and the operating temperature ageing.

The film resistance R_{film} is varied from 0.1 [$\Omega\cdot\text{cm}^2$] to 1 [$\text{k}\Omega\cdot\text{cm}^2$], (Fig. 3b). Varying the double layer capacitance C_{dl} between 10 [μFcm^{-2}] to 50 [μFcm^{-2}] (Fig. 3c) results mostly in a small increase in the height of the semicircle at intermediate frequencies (100 [mHz] – 1 [Hz]). Lastly, varying the particle radius on the positive electrode PR_{pos} between 100 [nm] to 900 [nm] reflects an increase in the slope of the diffusion tail in the Nyquist plot, see Fig. 3d. With the increase of the cathode particle radius the slope of the Warburg tail at low frequencies (right side of the Nyquist plot) increases, whereas minor or no changes are observed in the resistive or capacitive values at higher frequencies (mid-left side of the Nyquist plot). The change in the EIS tail slope at low frequencies was hardly evident in our EIS measurements for cycled cells at different conditions.

The here varied parameters show a very low cross-correlation on the calculated impedance spectrum and have very distinct effects at different frequency ranges. This allows us to use them as free parameters in a fitting routine of the experimentally obtained EIS spectra, as we will detail in section. However, including more free parameters would slowly

Fig. 3. FEM modelling of LIB. (a) Li-ion 1D model, based on the Newman physical equations, is used to describe the electrode interface processes including the electrochemistry of the anode (porous electrode 1), the cathode (porous electrode 2), and the electrolyte/separator. The model is used to fit different battery physical parameters, simulate EIS, and optimize the parameters when compared to measured battery impedance spectra. (b) Simulated impedance spectra while varying the film resistance (R_{film}) parameter in the model. (c) Simulated impedance spectra while varying the double layer capacitance (C_{dl}) parameter. (d) Simulated impedance spectra at different electrode particle radii.

lead to cross-correlation and ambiguous fitting results. Therefore, particularly the geometrical parameters have to be characterized independently.

2.3. Nano-characterization

As we discussed in the previous section, independent determination of geometric modelling parameters of the anode and cathode are required to avoid underdetermination of the model and to improve the overall matching of the FEM data to the experimental impedance spectra. Besides electrodes dimensions and their morphology, their conductive properties provide further valuable insights.

2.3.1. Morphology

Both SEM and all-electric AFM have been used to investigate the effect of ageing on the morphology and surface of the electrodes.

SEM micrographs of graphite electrodes were acquired for the fresh, 100-cycle and 900-cycle cells, at different magnification levels and are shown in Fig. 4. To prevent contamination and degradation, the cells were disassembled, and the samples were transferred and imaged in an inert atmosphere.

The low magnification images (Fig. 4a left column) show the graphite particles having a round-shaped morphology, while the high magnification images (Fig. 4a right column) exhibit the typical flake-like structure of the anode graphite surface. These graphite flakes, consisting of graphene layers linked by weak van der Waals forces and π - π interactions of the delocalized electron orbitals, are spread with various orientations on copper foils [50]. Due to this layered structure, graphite layers typically show a flake-like particle morphology [51]. The sub-structure of the graphite flakes gets visible at higher magnification ($\times 10000$). However, a striking difference between the differently cycled electrodes is not directly visible in these images.

In addition, high resolution all-electric AFM imaging has been used to characterize the anode sample surface with a nanometer resolution. In Fig. 4b, the obtained 3D reconstruction of the anode surface is shown. Images of LIB's cycled 0, 100, and 900 times are displayed. From the samples, four series of images with a scan size of 20, 10, 5 and 3 [μm] have been recorded at different sample positions, which allowed us to quantify the electrodes particle dimensions and roughness in an accurate way. The flake size was calculated to be 8 ± 0.3 [μm] for the graphite anode and 6 ± 3 [μm] for the NCA cathode and only minor changes of the particle radius were observed with the increase in the sample's number of cycles (Fig. S5). The values agree with the typical range of

particle radii reported in the literature for the NCA cathode [52,53], and the graphite anode [54].

A more detailed statistical analysis of the electrode roughness from SEM imaging (details reported in the Materials and Methods section) reveals finally a systematic increase of the anode roughness of up to 50% for the first 400 cycles (see root mean square roughness in Table 1 and Fig. 5a).

The relative increase of electrode roughness observed in the SEM data is confirmed by the analysis of the AFM images where we find an increase of the anode surface roughness from 15.45 ± 3.62 nm for fresh cells to 20 nm for 900 times cycled cells. We note, however, that the statistical relevance in AFM is poorer due to the high standard deviation (see Fig. 5a and Table 1). In contrast to the anode, no clear trend was observed on the roughness of the cycled cathode electrodes (see Fig. 4c and Table 1).

Finally, we used standard light microscopy to determine the individual thickness values for the anode, separator, and cathode layers, where we found no significant change of the layer thickness with higher cycling numbers. Fig. 5c (lower panel) shows the thickness of the different layers of a 18650 LIB. We note that the samples measured were double sides (i.e., a current collector coated with active material on both sides) and that the values are found to be in agreement with standard values given in the literature [10,55,56]. However, some deviations are typically due to the differences in the commercial cell producers, materials used, or machine tolerances during production [57].

Table 1

Results of the roughness analysis stated as root mean square values (RMS). Cycled LIBs are disassembled, and the electrodes surface roughness is characterized using SEM (percentage roughness) and all-electric AFM.

Nr. Of cycles	0	10	100	200	400	900
SEM RMS values for anode [%]	0%	6.2% ± 1.8	13.3% ± 2.0	36.6% ± 2.9	48.8% ± 2.2	55.2% ± 2.5
AFM RMS values for anode [nm]	15.45 ± 3.62	16.01 ± 3.48	20.47 ± 4.99	18.55 ± 7.48	17.23 ± 6.1	21.25 ± 7.67
AFM RMS values for cathode [nm]	80.76 \pm	85.33 \pm	76.4 ± 15.68	72.64 ± 8.93	79.14 ± 16.54	78.02 ± 16.27

Fig. 4. SEM and all-electric AFM imaging of cell components in cylindrical 18650 LIBs after cycling as indicated. (a) SEM images of increasingly cycled graphite anode surface with $500\times$ magnification (left) and $10000\times$ magnification (right). (b) 3D AFM images of the same anode sample surfaces as in a). (c) 3D AFM images of the LIBs cathodes cycled as in a).

Fig. 5. Roughness analysis of cycled anode and cathode LIB samples and determination of geometric parameters. (a) Roughness parameters have been extracted of anode samples from both AFM (blue, left axis) and SEM (red, right axis). For SEM percentage roughness increase from calibrated pixel values is shown, obtained from selected single μm sized flakes. AFM topographical imaging was used for the roughness analysis on small areas ($\sim 1 \mu\text{m}^2$). (b) Graphical representation of the AFM determined surface roughness of the cathode. (c) The thickness of different LIB components (anode, separator, and cathode) have been determined using light microscopy (bottom). For the determination of the particle radius both, AFM and SEM have been used (top). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

2.3.2. Electrical nano-characterization

We complement our topography images with electrical images of the cycled battery electrodes. Two different detection techniques were used in order to allow us to extract the conductivity of the electrodes at gigahertz (Fig. 6b) and DC frequencies (Fig. 6c). Both signals were acquired simultaneously with the AFM topography (Fig. 6a). While the DC conductance is very sensitive to small variations in the sample conductivity, it is limited to a certain conductance range. In contrast, the conductance measured at the gigahertz frequency range has a much higher dynamic range. The second advantage of the SMM method is its ability to measure the conductive properties of subsurface features, even if they are not in contact with a current collector.

In Fig. 6, we show representative images acquired for three different samples as indicated in the figure. The AFM topography of all samples exhibits similar grain structures as also observed in Fig. 4, though, in the conductance channels we notice sharp conducting features invisible in the topography analysis. Pristine sample 1 and sample 2, which was cycled for only 10 cycles, exhibit a bigger amount of these features. SMM allows us also to resolve further electric details in and around the conductive areas that are not visible by current sensing AFM. In the images of sample 4 (200 cycles), there are areas showing high conductance at microwave frequencies but no DC conduction. Based on the special capability of SMM to detect also conductive subsurface features we conclude that, this difference in the contrast is related to highly conductive electrode areas which have been disconnected from the rest of the carbon electrode by cracks and have no DC connection to the current collector anymore. Accordingly, the intercalation and de-intercalation of Li^+ ions result in volume changes of the active material [58], these volume changes lead to cracks in the SEI and weaken the particle-to-particle contacts as well as breakage of C-C bonds in the graphite. A study by Lin et al., shows that with cell ageing cracks occur in the bulk of the graphite particles and subsequently along the grain

boundaries on the direction parallel to the current collector, potentially due to stress-induced during lithiation and de-lithiation cycles [59].

3. Discussion: combining FEM with SPM and EIS

Finally, we want to combine the FEM with the additional information obtained from scanning probe microscopy (SPM) measurements (such as roughness, particle size, and thickness of the different layers) in order to have a robust physical model for extracting from EIS data the change of current density, double layer capacitance, and film resistance during ageing. These free parameters are uncorrelated with each other, and all fixed parameters could be determined from direct measurements, such as SoC and temperature. Besides the geometric parameters, we could directly estimate with our measurements several other battery parameters in the model, some of which are obtained from literature as we indicate in Table 2.

We selected EIS spectra, acquired at 60% SoC on 0 to 800 times cycled batteries, and fit the 1D LIB FEM model to the experimental data. Each dataset at a specific cycle level was fitted separately using appropriate starting values, based on information obtained from literature and prior experience on similar cells, and four fitting parameters, namely exchange current density, double layer capacitance at the electrodes, cathode particle diameter, and the resistance of the interface film layers.

Fig. 7a, shows the Nyquist plots of the simulated (solid lines) and experimentally obtained EIS data, acquired at different cycles which exhibit a good agreement. As shown earlier in Fig. 1, in a battery EIS spectrum we generally have two semicircles, one related to the electrode film (SEI) represented by R_{film} and C_{if} , and the other related to charge-transfer resistance with R_{ct} and C_{dl} . After ageing, the electrode interface film mainly on the anode side increases in thickness upon cycling, and as a consequence R_{film} increases, though C_{if} decreases over cycling ($C = \epsilon A/d$, where ϵ is the permittivity, A is the surface area, and d is the

Fig. 6. Electrical scanning probe microscopy of differently aged battery anodes. a) AFM topography acquired in contact mode. b) Normalized SMM conductance measured at 2.78 GHz. Details on the normalization are reported in the experimental section. c) DC Conductance simultaneously obtained by current sensing AFM. Representative images of three samples after 0, 100, and 200 cycles are shown.

Table 2

The main fixed and free parameter estimates that are used for the FEM battery model.

Fixed Parameters	Estimate
Diffusion coefficient (D) [$\text{cm}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Electrolyte phase: $D_0 \cdot \exp\left(\frac{R}{298 - \frac{1}{T}}\right)$, where D_0 and R are constants, and T is the temperature in Kelvin Anode phase: $6.8e^{-15}$ Cathode phase: $1.5e^{-15}$
Electrolyte conductivity [S m^{-1}]	$\sigma_0 \cdot \exp\left(\frac{K}{298 - \frac{1}{T}}\right)$, where σ_0 , is a constant, and T is the temperature in Kelvin (K)
Electrolyte concentration (c_{el})	1200 [mol m^{-3}]
Active material particle radius	Anode: 8 ± 0.3 [μm]; measured with AFM Cathode: 6 ± 3 [μm]; measured with AFM
Thickness of different layers	For the anode 135 ± 2 [μm], for the cathode 103 ± 2 [μm] and for the separator 15.1 ± 1 [μm]
Electrode area	620 [cm^2], measured after cell disassembly
SoC	60%, measured with Coulomb counting
Cell surface temperature	298 K, monitored using a PT1000 sensor
Free Parameters	Estimate
Exchange current density (I_0)	0.19–0.28 [mA cm^{-2}]; cycle dependent
Double layer capacitance (C_{dl})	12–18 [$\mu\text{F cm}^{-2}$]; cycle dependent
Film resistance (R_{film})	52–72 [Ωcm^2]; cycle dependent
Anode particle radius (Pr_{neg})	7.6–8.4 [$\mu\text{F.cm}^{-2}$]

thickness). Conversely, R_{ct} and C_{dl} both increase with the cycling of the cells due (mainly) to the degradation and increase in the electrode's roughness. In Fig. 7a we note that, upon cycling, the spectra in the complex impedance plane shifts progressively to lower frequencies, *i.e.*, to the right of the Nyquist plot and slightly increases in height and width of the depressed semi-circle. The estimated parameters obtained from the model for each of the cycles are shown in Fig. 7 b, c, d, and e, respectively. Fig. 7b shows a strong correlation between the double layer capacitance, C_{dl} , and the average anode roughness of the anode electrode measured by AFM. Furthermore, the particle radius of the anode electrode in Fig. 7d shows the same trend as the one obtained from the AFM measurements, and it is relatively stable with increasing cycles. The exchange current density, I_0 , is decaying with the number of cycles (Fig. 7c). Lastly, the film resistance, R_{film} , shows an increasing value with the cycles increase (Fig. 7e); the ohmic resistance increases potentially due to the increase of the SEI thickness, and the degradation in the electrolyte conduction or the electrode contact [60,61].

The presented results demonstrate the robustness of the combined EIS/FEM/microscopy approach to follow battery ageing, which can be implemented in future, also, to systematically explore the effect of the SoC on the extracted parameters and the temperature influence of the ageing. The temperature has an important effect on the ageing processes as we have clearly visualized in the EIS spectra in Fig. 2c. The workflow to follow the temperature-induced changes on the electrode structure, including the cross-validation by microscopy techniques, would be very similar to the one presented here. However, to cross-validate the morphological and electrical properties at different states of charge, microscopy techniques like SECM [17] or ec-SMM [36], operating *in-situ* are required.

Furthermore, the results show that the method can be considered as a promising approach to evaluate ageing mechanisms of real cells, while

Fig. 7. Extraction of ageing-related parameters from EIS spectra, FEM, and microscopy, and comparison to results obtained from post-mortem battery samples. (a) Experimental EIS spectra (scatter points) of cycle aged LIB compared to EIS simulation results (solid lines). EIS conditions are frequency 1 mHz to 1 kHz, temperature 24 °C and SoC 60%, $U = 10$ mV. The inductive effects at high frequencies (>1 kHz) are not simulated. (b) The double layer capacitance (C_{dl}) parameter at the electrodes (left axis, blue) extracted from the optimized FEM model fit for different battery cycles is compared to the electrode surface roughness obtained from AFM measurements (right axis, red). (c) Fitted exchange current density, I_0 , as a function of cycle numbers. (d) Fitted anode particle radius as a function of cycle number is compared to the particle radius obtained from AFM measurement (e) Fitted film resistance, R_{film} , is shown as a function of cycle number. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

in operation. The in-line estimation of the point of charge of the cell is derived by the acquisition of EIS spectra, which are evaluated through the modelled data obtained in the first step of the developed method. This can facilitate an optimized sorting process for second life modules and cells based on the same chemistries [62]. In addition, a deeper understanding of the cell characteristics and states can be obtained, in order to widen the operation window of batteries within modules and packs for electric vehicle (EV) applications.

As described earlier, the developed method allows combining *in-situ* observations with modelled data paving the way for cell real-time monitoring and management system optimisation. For instance, cloud-based battery management systems (BMS) can be foreseen as a suitable approach for monitoring cell characteristics, integrating big data techniques and model-based approaches, where especially efficient multi-scale integrated modelling methods are required like the multi-physics finite element model (FEM) used in this manuscript [46,63]. It is proven that battery models are key components of today's BMS [64]. Currently, the state-of-the-art shows that BMSs are tending towards applying physics-based battery models in the system as they provide a better estimation of the cell voltage and allow the calculation of power limits based on physical reactions rather than conservative specifications obtained from lookup tables [65]. Therefore, further research will follow on adapting the presented methods combined with physics-based modelling for BMS, for example by simplifying the presented model to a reduced model in state-space.

4. Conclusion

We successfully combined EIS, FEM multi-physics modelling, and advanced microscopy techniques to follow electrochemical cycling ageing in LIBs. The non-destructive EIS method can clearly trace ageing effects at different frequency ranges, however, a direct and unambiguous relation to changes in the relevant electrochemical parameters is challenging due to the cross-correlation of multiple chemical and geometrical parameters in the used finite element model. We, therefore, determined in an initial step the relevant geometrical battery parameter (electrode/separator thicknesses, particle diameters) using microscopy methods. This led to a clear reduction of the number of free parameters

in the FEM and enabled us to reliably fit the FEM and the measured EIS data in order to extract a change of a set of battery electrochemical parameters.

We systematically followed the effects of ageing at different SoC for up to 900 electrochemical cycles and observed that the main electric parameters directly influenced by the cycling were the exchange current density, film resistance, and double layer capacitance. While the film resistance and double layer capacitance clearly increased with ageing, the overall exchange current density started to drop. Local morphological and electrical changes on the cycled batteries were also investigated by AFM, SEM, and SMM techniques. The results showed a correlation between the increasing anode double layer capacitance and the electrode's roughness. Moreover, based on the SMM capability to detect conductive subsurface features, we observed some areas, in the hundred's nanometer range, showing high conductance at microwave frequencies but no DC conduction. The differences, in contrast, are potentially related to highly conductive electrode areas which were disconnected from the carbon electrode by cracks, due to ageing, and have no DC connection to the current collector. The highly relevant influence of temperature and SoC on the electrochemical parameters and the ageing itself will be in the scope of future research.

5. Materials and Methods

5.1. Cell cycling and disassembling

In this work, 18650 cylindrical cells with a 2.5 Ah rated discharge capacity at 0.2C current load were used. The cells are based on a LiNi-CoAlO₂ (NCA) cathode and a graphite-based composite anode. The cells have copper (Cu) and aluminium (Al) current collectors for the anode and cathode, respectively, a separator and liquid electrolyte.

The applied electrochemical cycling method consisted of charging the cell with a constant current constant voltage (CC-CV) method followed by a 1C (2.5 A) constant discharge until reaching the lower voltage limit (2.8 V vs Li⁺/Li). The CV part consists of charging the battery at the higher voltage limit of 4.2 V vs Li⁺/Li and then a CC part is applied until the current drops to 1C/20 (125 mA), see Fig. 8. The cycling process is continued with 8 min rest time in between cycles.

Fig. 8. CC-CV battery charging method, with the related voltage and current profiles for a 18650 cell. The voltage limits are 3.1 V vs Li^+/Li to 4.2 V vs Li^+/Li and a 1.25 A (0.5C) current is applied.

Once a desired cycle number is reached the cell is detached from the cycler, fully discharged, and prepared for cell opening and disassembling. Once the desired cycle number was achieved, the cell was set to 100% SoC (Fig. 2a), by charging the cell using the CC-CV method (with a 0.5C charging current for the CC part) up to 4.2 V vs Li^+/Li and a C/20 cut-off current for the CV part. EIS was then performed after the cell was kept in a resting period for >120 min at 24 °C in a climatic chamber. Similarly, in the SoC measurement (shown in Fig. 2b), the battery was first fully charged by a CC-CV method up to 4.2 V Li^+/Li and kept resting at 24 °C for >120 min, then EIS was conducted at 5-SoC values. The SoC was changed by discharging the cell with a low current (0.5C), using Coulombs counting, and the battery was kept resting for 20 min before EIS was measured. Impedance spectroscopy analyses were also conducted on cells cycled at different operating temperatures (Fig. 2c). The cells were kept in a climatic chamber at 10 °C, 24 °C, and 45 °C, respectively; and then, 100 charge-discharge cycles were performed. The charged cells were afterwards kept resting at room temperature (24 °C) for >24 h, and EIS was measured at room temperature.

The cycled cells were disassembled in a commercial glovebox (~40 L volume) specially designed for AFM imaging (Keysight glovebox). The glovebox was placed in a hood with an argon atmosphere while maintaining oxygen and humidity levels sufficiently below 1%. The discharged batteries, disassembling tools, cleaning agents, and material to pack and seal the samples were all pre-set in the glovebox. The glovebox was connected to an argon tank (Argon 5.0, Linde, Linz, Austria) and flooded with 2–3 L/min for at least 1 h. For safety reasons, laboratory gloves were worn in addition to the standard rubber gloves. Prior to cell disassembling, the cell was fully discharged (within the voltage limits of the standard operations) using a similar C-rate as used for the cycling process to maintain the original cycling effects intact. While cell cutting, the outer foil of the battery was first peeled using a cutter. The metal conversion was then opened using a steel pipe cutter. Afterwards, the negative connector tab of the battery including the fuse was carefully cut and removed. The metal conversion was fully opened using a side cutter and needle-nose pliers. The opened battery was rolled out and several samples of the anode electrode (copper foil with both side carbon coating) were cut from different locations. Cathode samples of about 0.5 × 0.5 cm were cut using a scissor. Each sample was extensively rinsed with dimethyl carbonate (Merck KGaA, Darmstadt) to remove any electrolyte residues (Fig. S6) [66]. After rinsing, the samples were dried under a gentle stream of argon. Each sample was placed in a petri-dish and sealed with parafilm, while under argon atmosphere. All samples were immediately transferred to the measurement setups and stored in

the measurement gloveboxes for further use. Once the samples were opened, they were measured immediately.

5.2. Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS)

The impedance measurement equipment setup consists of an excitation signal generation, as a multi-frequency sinusoidal source or an arbitrary waveform generator (AWG), followed by a power amplifier that delivers the desired voltage or current amplitude to stimulate the battery under test (BUT). The excitation signal is provided by the equipment's "force" terminal, and the BUT response is measured through the "sense" terminals in a 4-wire configuration setup to compensate for any voltage drop along the wires. With low impedance batteries, current mode excitation (galvanostatic mode) is preferred while current amplitudes can be in the range of 10 mA up to 100 A. Coaxial wiring for both, force and sense connections, is considered and significantly reduces the susceptibility to cable referred systematic and random errors. Moreover, a BUT test fixture is specially designed for cylindrical cell battery forms, providing a direct contact from the 4-wire terminals to the BUT, and includes a safety printed circuit board (PCB) designed to protect the BUT and user from high voltages, currents, or extreme temperatures (see Fig. S7 in the Supplementary Information).

In this work, the battery impedance spectrum was measured through the galvanostatic method. This was done by feeding a sinusoidal current into the battery terminals while measuring the voltage response across the terminals. The current (I) and voltage (V) signals are digitized and transformed into the frequency domain where the actual impedance is calculated by $Z(\omega) = V(\omega)/I(\omega)$, where ω is the angular frequency. Frequency sweeping was used to cover the broad spectrum from 10 mHz up to 5 kHz. Before starting an EIS measurement, the cell was mounted on the cylindrical cell fixture which in turn was set in a controlled climatic chamber. Initially, EIS was performed on three cells, to verify the repeatability and consistency of the cells (see Fig. S8 in the Supplementary Information). The fixture was connected to the EIS instruments via coaxial wires in a 4-wire Kelvin connection scheme. The cell is kept resting at the desired temperature for >1 h to slowly adapt to the ambient temperature, and then the EIS measurements are conducted at 5 SoCs every 100-cycles. The EIS measurement settings, for each data set collection, are performed by applying a logarithmic ascending frequency sweep starting from 10 mHz up to 5 kHz, while measuring 9 points per decade, and using a 90-mA peak-to-peak excitation current. A total time span of about 17 min is logged for each EIS data set collection. Moreover, several factors were considered to maintain consistency between the different EIS measurements by following a consistent cycling/measurement protocol. In some instances, the measured EIS can be affected by whether the last step applied on the BUT was a charge or discharge process, which is related to the open-circuit voltage hysteresis effect [67,68]. In addition, a rest period is also necessary when the temperature of the cell is adjusted in order to maintain thermal equilibrium; this rest time can differ if the change in temperature (ΔT) is larger, and also depends on the direction of the applied temperature change (i.e., increase or decrease) [69]. To overcome such effects, a sufficient rest time was provided to have the cell at a stationary condition [1,70]. The illustration of the EIS spectra was done using a complex impedance graph with a flipped imaginary axis (i.e. Nyquist plot). Where the positive imaginary impedance corresponds to the inductive phenomena originating from the current collectors, rolling of the battery electrodes in cylindrical cells, and the cell interconnections. The negative imaginary impedance is related to the capacitive phenomena such as the electrode/electrolyte interphase reactions, the formation of the charge-double-layer capacitance, and the charge transfer resistances. The intersection point of the spectra with the x-axis reflects the ohmic resistance (R_{sol} and R_{film}) due to the electrolyte and electrode interface resistances. A depressed semicircle in the Nyquist plot implies that multi-processes occur with similar relaxation time constants, in contrast to an ideal semi-circle representing the activation-energy controlled

charge transfer process. Lastly, the spectra tail at low frequencies represents the slow process diffusion phenomena of the ions in the liquid and solid phases.

5.3. Atomic force microscopy (AFM)

5.3.1. Glove box for AFM imaging

A glove box with a chamber dimension of $120 \times 50 \times 60 \text{ cm}^3$ (length/width/height) resulting in a volume of 360 L and a lock with dimensions of $25 \times 22 \times 20 \text{ cm}^3$ (length/width/height) giving a volume of 13.2 L was designed. All parts were made from acrylic glass and were ordered from Firstlaser GmbH (Bardowick, Germany) and self-assembled using transparent acrylic glue and clean room silicone Otto-seal S68 (Daniel Maas Dichtstoffhandel, Kevelaer, Germany). The glove box was equipped with gloves from bromobutyl rubber with a thickness of 0.4 mm (Jung Rubbertec, Einhausen, Germany). For filling and flow control the box was equipped with three micro float flow meter, KFR-2112-N0 (0.04–0.5 L/min), KFR-2214-N0 (0.4–5 L/min, KFR-2117-N0 (6–50L/in) from Kobold Holding GmbH (Vienna, Austria).

The glove box was pre-filled with nitrogen using a flow of *circa* 10 L/min for about 3 h to reach 0% humidity and oxygen content. Humidity and oxygen contents were measured using GMH3351-GE for the humidity and GMH3695-GE for the oxygen content (GHM Messtechnik GmbH, Remscheid, Germany). Afterwards, the glove box was filled with argon for about 2 h with a flowing stream of 5 L/min. During AFM measurements the flow was reduced to 0.5 L/min to maintain the AFM system stable. Self-made cable feed-throughs were used to connect and supply instruments in the glovebox.

To prevent the samples from degradation, they were packed and sealed under an argon atmosphere, and the glove box was only opened before the sample preparation process. The sealed samples were transferred to the all-electric AFM measuring glove box. Here, the box was first filled with nitrogen to reach a humidity and oxygen level of below 1000 ppm (<1%) using a constant flow of 20 L/min for about 3 h, which is about $10\times$ the follow of the glove box. Subsequently, the nitrogen gas was replaced by argon. Therefore, the home build glove box was flooded with argon for 1 h at 20 L/min. After filling the glove box with argon for all other preparations and measurements, the flow was reduced to about 2 L/min to keep a low but constant pressure in the glove box. A possible influence of the gentle stream of argon was verified with noise measurements. The results are comparable to our formerly done noise measurements using all-electric AFM in ambient conditions [71], and no influence could be found.

5.3.2. AFM system

All different LIB samples were transferred sealed and under argon atmosphere to the glove box through the lock system. After filling the glove box with argon, the samples were unpacked and mounted to the sample holder for imaging. For AFM topographical imaging we used an all-electric AFM (AFSEM®) from GETec Microscopy GmbH (Vienna, Austria). This system was designed to be used in the vacuum chamber of a scanning electron microscope; therefore, slight adjustments were necessary. To maintain stabilization and reduce noise, a heavy metal plate was positioned in the glove box. The AFM scanner was mounted to a z-stage by a dovetail adapter and, furthermore, to a damped rod (Newport, Deckenpfronn, Germany) which was is screwed to the heavy plate. The Z-axis approach of the scanner was done by a fully automated z-stage using a 2" piezo motor (Newport, Deckenpfronn, Germany). Sample positioning in the X and Y axis was done using a motorized microscopy table with joystick control (Märzhäuser, Wetzlar, Germany). A self-made cable feed-through was used to connect the AFM scanner inside the glove box to the controller outside. An enlarged nose cone with increased z-range was constructed. The larger z-range ($\sim 10 \mu\text{m}$) was necessary for larger z-scan size images of the anode samples due to the high roughness between different carbon flakes. For intermittent contact mode imaging, a $2 \times 2 \times 2 \text{ mm}$ piezo (P.I. Ceramics GmbH,

Lederhose, Germany) for acoustic excitation was mounted through a hole from the top of the cone, positioned as close as possible to the sensor. All images were recorded in phase optimized intermittent contact mode using PRSA $100 \times 48 \mu\text{m}$ or PRSA $300 \times 100 \mu\text{m}$ self-sensing cantilever (SCL. Sensor. Tech, Vienna, Austria). The PRSA $100 \times 48 \mu\text{m}$ were used at the fundamental frequency, whereas the PRSA $300 \times 100 \mu\text{m}$ cantilevers were driven at their 3rd harmonic. All used self-sensing cantilevers are equipped with two active piezo-resistors integrated on the cantilever and two passive piezo-resistors integrated on the chip. These four resistors are connected to a Wheatstone bridge, and the resistance was about 1 k Ω each for all cantilevers used.

5.3.3. AFM imaging and analysis

For all-electric AFM measurements, the anode samples were glued onto a sample holder using double-sided tape and mounted on a fully automated table. Here all-electric AFM imaging using self-sensing cantilever technology provided leverage as no optical alignment was necessary, which is difficult using gloves. AFM imaging was performed in intermittent contact mode using a self-sensing cantilever with a resonance frequency of 250–550 kHz and a spring constant between 14 and 170 N/m. For all differently cycled batteries (0–900 cycles), two samples from each battery were used for topographical imaging. For each sample at least 10 images with a scan size of 10, 3, and 1.5 μm were obtained. Image analysis was performed using the SPM freeware program Gwyddion for 3D reconstruction and Mountainsmap 7.4 (Digital Surf, Besancon, France) for the roughness analysis.

In the flat sample regions, representing carbon flakes, manual extraction of the roughness was done. After manual cutting of areas of about 1 μm^2 , applying a flattening and line alignment algorithm the root mean square values (RMS) were extracted. About 25 different positions for each differently cycled battery sample were determined to calculate the RMS mean value and the standard deviation.

5.4. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and analysis

After sample preparation was done, one sample of each LIB was glued to an SEM stub using double side carbon tape. The stubs were mounted to a standard SEM sample holder. Following the sample preparation under an argon atmosphere, the sample holder was transferred to the SEM chamber immediately. All images were recorded using a Philips XL30 SEM. First, an overview image was taken, and then several images on different positions using $\times 500$ and $\times 1000$ magnifications were recorded using both, detection of secondary as well as the detection of backscattered electrons. All SEM images were recorded using 10 kV acceleration voltage. Keeping the parameters constant for all images, including working distance, contrast, and brightness, allowed for an accurate RMS roughness analysis and comparable values.

5.4.1. Glove box and SMM/C-AFM system design

The glove box for scanning microwave microscopy (SMM) imaging was produced in a similar way as that for AFM imaging, though, with reduced dimensions: $60 \times 40 \times 40 \text{ cm}$ (length/width/height), resulting in a volume of 96 L. According to the reduced volume, the filling time for both nitrogen and argon was decreased by a factor of three.

Scanning microwave microscopy is a non-destructive, near-field electrical characterization technique combining the nanoscale resolution of the atomic force microscope with the broadband capabilities of the vector network analyzer (VNA). For operation, a conductive AFM tip is connected to the VNA through a coaxial line. A shunt and the portion of the line towards the tip create a series of resonant notches, and the measurement frequency is selected close to the minima of the resonant notches. In this way, good matching and a high signal-to-noise ratio can be achieved.

The AFM provides a topography image while the VNA measures the S_{11} reflection coefficient. Which is a vector ratio of reflected and inci-

dent microwave signals. The reflected signal at tip-sample interface depends on complex permittivity $\hat{\epsilon}(\omega) = \epsilon'(\omega) + j\epsilon''(\omega)$, (where ϵ' is the real part of permittivity, ϵ'' is the complex part, and ω is the angular frequency), and the conductivity of the material. For every point of topography phase and amplitude of the S_{11} parameter is obtained from the VNA.

In our experiments, we combined SMM with current sensing AFM. Therefore, a Bias-T was inserted into the transmission line after the shunt and the sample was biased at 5 mV. A *trans*-impedance amplifier with amplification of 1 V/10 nA was connected to the bias T and the amplifier's output was connected to the AUX input of the AFM. This setup allowed us to probe DC conductivity and S_{11} simultaneously. Measurement frequency was set to 8.323 GHz, and the probes used were full platinum Rocky Mountain Nanotech, with a nominal tip radius of 80 nm and a spring constant of 18 N/m.

5.5. Finite element method modelling (FEM)

Finite element method (FEM) modelling was carried out with COMSOL Multiphysics 5.4 using the electrochemical toolbox. The 1D-Newman model was used to describe the electrochemical processes. In this model, the current was the output, and voltage and temperature were the inputs. The main equations of this 1D-Newman model described the non-isothermal charge/discharge process including the lithium material balance in the electrolyte, double layer capacitance at electrode materials, the electrode film resistance, the ionic concentration, the particle radius of the active material, the exchange current flowing in the electrolyte, the current density in the electrode and the superficial current density of the cell. This 1D electrochemistry model, illustrated in Fig. 3 a, considered NCA cathode electrode with 103 μm length, graphite (Li_xC_6 MCMB) anode electrode with 135 [μm] length, polymer electrolyte (1.2 M LiPF₆ in EC: EMC solvent (3:7 by weight), and separator (Celgard 2325) with 15.11 μm length (the physical parameters were experimentally obtained using the AFM technique on extracted battery samples).

The model used a Comsol solver to simulate the impedance spectrum of the 1D model for a wide range of battery physical/chemical parameters. A fitting procedure was written in Mathematica that optimized the main ageing parameters (e.g., film resistance, double layer capacitance, exchange current, and particle radius) to fit with the data. Considering suitable voltage perturbation values, applied in EIS, with small current response values, the model equations could be linearized, and then the Laplace transform was applied. The model equations were then formulated in the frequency domain with complex variables. The Comsol Multiphysics software automatically performed both the linearization around a given potential and current and the transform. The EIS, in this work, was modelled while using a voltage perturbation of 100 mV with a frequency sweep, based on the experimental data, from 10 mHz to 1 kHz. Though, the inductive effects at high frequencies, e.g. due to metallic connectors, were not modelled.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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Nomenclature

A: surface area (m^2)
C_{dl}: double layer capacitance (F cm^{-2})
C_{el}: Electrolyte concentration (mol m^{-3})
C_{if}: interface capacitance (F cm^{-2})
D: Diffusion coefficient ($\text{cm}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$)
d: Thickness (m)
I₀: Exchange current density (mA cm^{-2})
j: Imaginary unit
K: Ionic conductivity (S cm^{-1})
r_{pos}: particle radius on the positive electrode (m)
r_{neg}: particle radius on the negative electrode (m)
R: Gas constant ($\text{J mol}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$)
R_{ct}: charge transfer resistance (Ωcm^2)
R_{film}: interface resistance (Ωcm^2)
R_{sol}: solution resistance (Ωcm^2)
S₁₁: reflection coefficient (dB)
T: temperature (Kelvin, K)
 ϵ^* : complex permittivity (F cm^{-1})
 ϵ'' : complex part of permittivity (F cm^{-1})
 ϵ' : real part of permittivity (F cm^{-1})
 σ : Conductivity (S cm^{-1})

ω : Angular frequency (rad s^{-1})
 ϵ : Permittivity (F cm^{-1})

Glossary

AFM: Atomic force microscopes
RMS: root mean square
BUT: Battery under test
SECM: Scanning electrochemical microscopy
CC-CV: constant current constant voltage
SEI: solid electrolyte interface
DCIR: direct current internal resistance
SEM: Scanning electron microscope
EIS: Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy
SMM: scanning microwave microscopy
Ex situ: off-site
SoC: state of charge
FEM: finite element model
TEM: Transmission electron microscope
In situ: in place
VNA: vector network analyser
LIB: lithium-ion battery